

A New Sensitive Method for Determination of 4-Nitrophenylhydrazine using a New Reagent System

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A new sensitive method for the determination of 4-nitrophenylhydrazine has been proposed. The method is based on the oxidation of 4-nitrophenylhydrazine to 4-nitrophenyldiazonium chloride with selenious acid in strong HCl medium. The diazonium salt is then coupled with *N*-(1-naphthyl)ethylenediamine (NEDA) in HCl medium. Violet dye formed is measured at 545 nm against reagent blank. The reaction is fast, sensitive, and reproducible. It is simple and does not require rigid control of conditions. Acidity, temperature, time and reagent concentrations have been studied for the full colour development. Various analytical parameters, such as Beer's law, molar absorptivity, etc., have been evaluated.

HYDRAZINE derivatives are highly reactive and toxic^{1,2}. Phenylhydrazine is a useful reagent which acts as intermediate in the synthesis of many organic chemicals. Phenyl derivative of hydrazine causes systemic injury¹. Several analytical methods have been proposed for the determination of aryl hydrazines³⁻⁷. These methods suffer from interferences of other hydrazine derivatives and are time consuming.

In the present investigation, the method for the determination of selenium⁸ has been modified for the determination of 4-nitrophenylhydrazine. The proposed method is based on the oxidation of 4-nitrophenylhydrazine to 4-nitrophenyldiazonium chloride with selenious acid in strong hydrochloric acid medium, which is then coupled with *N*-(1-naphthyl)ethylenediamine in hydrochloric acid medium. The violet dye formed is measured at 545 nm against a reagent blank. The optimum reaction conditions and various analytical parameters have been evaluated.

Experimental

ECIL GS 865 spectrophotometer and Carl Zeiss Spekol with 1 cm matched silica cells were used for spectrophotometric measurements. A thermostatted water-bath was used.

A stock solution of standard 4-nitrophenylhydrazine solution (4-NPH) (1 mg ml⁻¹) was prepared. Working standards were prepared by appropriate dilution. A 0.05% selenium solution was prepared. A 0.2% solution of *N*-(1-naphthyl)ethylenediamine (NEDA) was prepared and kept in amber coloured volumetric flask. All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. Double-distilled water was used throughout the work.

Procedure: An aliquot of 4-nitrophenylhydrazine (10-60 µg) solution was transferred to a

graduated test tube. To it was added selenium solution (1 ml) and acidity of the solution was maintained around 6 *M* HCl. The test tube was kept in a thermostatted water-bath (60±2°) for 15 min. The solution was then transferred to a 25 ml standard volumetric flask. To it was added NEDA solution (1 ml). The solution was made upto the mark with 5 *N* HCl and kept for 10 min for complete colour development. The absorbance of the violet dye formed was measured at 545 nm and the amount of 4-NPH calculated from the calibration curve.

Results and Discussion

The absorbance of the reagent blank and dye were measured at 545 nm. The reagent blank has negligible absorbance at this wavelength, hence all spectral measurements were done against distilled water.

Colour reaction: 4-Nitrophenylhydrazine is oxidised to 4-nitrophenyldiazonium chloride by Se^{IV} in strong HCl medium, itself being reduced to elemental selenium. NEDA then reacts with 4-nitrophenyl diazonium chloride to give a violet dye. The colour reaction can be explained as

The effect of various concentration of selenium solution was studied by adding the reagent to

4-NPH solution in different molar ratios and developing the colour as described in the procedure. It was found that 1 : 1 molar ratio of reagent and 4-NPH is required for full colour development and absorbance remains constant at the above ratio. The mole ratio between diazonium salt and coupling reagent NEDA for complete reaction was studied and found to be 1 : 20.

Effect of variables : Acidity : The effect of acidity on oxidation of 4-NPH was studied by maintaining different molarity of HCl ranging from 1 to 7 M and developing the colour as recommended in procedure. This study revealed that at least 5 M HCl was required for complete oxidation. Above this range constant absorbance values were obtained. Our experiments were carried out at 6 M HCl.

Effect of temperature and time : The reaction was carried out at temperature range 25–70°. The minimum time required for complete oxidation was evaluated by allowing the oxidation reaction for different time intervals and developing colour as recommended. It was found that the reaction was accelerated with the rise in temperature, as the same being attained in 10 min at 60° and 45 min at 25°. However, the stability of diazonium chloride decreases at higher temperature and so our experiments were carried out at 60° after 15 min.

Beer's law, molar absorptivity, Sandell's sensitivity and reproducibility : The colour system was found to obey Beer's law in the range 0.4–2.4 ppm of 4-NPH at 545 nm. The regression analysis of absorbance on concentration gave regression coefficient of 0.013 5 with correlation coefficient of 0.99 and intercept of 0.000. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity were found to be $5.00 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.003 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$, respectively.

The reproducibility of the method was checked by replicate analysis of a standard solution of 4-NPH over a period of 7 days. The results showed that the method is fairly reproducible. The data were employed to compute the standard deviation and relative standard deviation, which were found to be $\pm 0.005 3$ and $\pm 1.40\%$, respectively.

Effect of foreign species : To check the validity of the method 30 μg of 4-NPH was determined in presence of known amounts of interferents which are supposed to be present along with 4-NPH. Phenylhydrazine and 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine do not interfere when present in 50- and 100-fold excess, respectively. For the estimation of 1.2 ppm of 4-nitrophenylhydrazine the tolerance limit of several other interferents and certain metal ions (in ppm) that cause $\pm 2\%$ error are as follows : cyanide (100), carbonate (100), sulphate (100), phosphate (100), Ba^{II} (50), Ca^{II} (50), Ni^{II} (50), Zn^{II} (50), Pb^{II} (50), Al^{III} (50), hydrazine (50), phenylhydrazine (50), 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine (100), phenol (2 000), formaldehyde (2 000), hydrocarbons (2 000).

The method is simple, sensitive, and free from rigid control of conditions and several common interferences. It can be employed for the estimation of 4-nitrophenylhydrazine in biological material and in air.

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